

OPEN SCIENCE + FAIR DATA MANAGEMENT SECTIONS IN THE PROPOSAL - HORIZON EUROPE - QUICK PRACTICAL GUIDE

Horizon Europe is quite different compared to Horizon 2020 in terms of Open Science provisions. In particular:

- Horizon Europe includes **Open Science (no longer only Open Access)** as a **Methodology in Part B section 1-Excellence**
- **Open Science adoption** in your research workflow is part of the **evaluation criteria of your proposal**
- there are **mandatory practices** and **recommended practices, both to be addressed** in the Methodology section of the proposal
- as for **publications, Open Access fees in hybrid journals** (=traditional subscription based journals [Elsevier, Wiley, Springer Nature...] offering an Open Choice to publish 1 article Open Access upon payment of APC, Article Processing Charges) **are no longer eligible for reimbursement**
- as for **data**, you need to be compliant a) with the **Open Data Directive** (EU 1024/2019, in Italy: D.Lgs. 200/2021) stating that research **data generated by public funds must be “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”** (= open by default, you have to justify with sound reasons if you keep them closed) b) with the **FAIR principles**, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

In a nutshell

OPEN SCIENCE (max 1 page)	MANDATORY PRACTICES	Describe how you'll be compliant to <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Immediate Open Access to texts [3 options: ORE, full OA journal, traditional journal+rights retention] 2) FAIR data management + “as open as possible” rule; data deposited in a “trusted repository” 3) Data Management Plan due by month 6 4) Measures to a) validate the results b) reproduce your research
	RECOMMENDED PRACTICES	Add all the relevant Open practices to your research workflow. If you reckon that none applies, you have to justify.
FAIR DATA MANAGEMENT (max 1 page)	DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN SCHEMA [beware: you have to actually give specific indications here, not simply state that the DMP “will contain” this information]	Specify in a bullet point list <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the type of data the project will be reusing (if so) • the type of data the project is going to generate and their format • the expected size of data [there might be costs associated to storage and preservation, and you must budget them] • Findable: which persistent identifiers; which metadata schema to describe the data; versioning • Accessible: which formats; which access conditions [Open=the default, if not, you have to justify] • Interoperable: which standards; which ontologies • Reusable: documentation to ensure a safe reuse; licenses to enable reuse • Ethical + GDPR related issues + any other legal aspect • Costs • Responsibilities and techniques for storage, backup and long term preservation • Whether you will hire a data steward or not/who is taking care of FAIR data management

OPEN SCIENCE (max 1 page)

In this section you need to address

- a) how you will be **compliant with the 4 mandatory Open practices**
- b) how you will **adopt recommended Open practices**

4 MANDATORY PRACTICES	PROVISION	OPTIONS	WHAT YOU HAVE TO DO	NOTES
1) PUBLICATIONS	IMMEDIATE OPEN ACCESS (no embargo* allowed)	a) PUBLISH IN ORE (OPEN RESEARCH EUROPE), THE EU PUBLISHING PLATFORM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - submit your preprint to ORE - follow the internal ORE workflow, no need for other repositories, deposit is included - you are compliant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - no costs - open peer review included as ORE operates with Open peer review - it's a platform, not a journal, BUT research assessment criteria are changing (see COARA, it's very important)
		b) PUBLISH IN A FULL OPEN ACCESS JOURNAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - select your full Open Access journal in DOAJ - publishing there will give immediate Open Access - deposit your paper in an open Access repository [for text and data mining, not for access] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 36% of the journals in DOAJ asks APCs, Article Processing Charges - full OA journals APCs are eligible for reimbursement - you need to budget the costs in the proposal - BEWARE: you can choose also an HYBRID OPEN ACCESS JOURNAL (=subscription based journals offering to publish 1 single article Open): 100% requires APCs [up to 12.290 \$ at Nature] BUT THE COSTS ARE NOT ELIGIBLE FOR REIMBURSEMENT
		c) PUBLISH IN A TRADITIONAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - search for the journal copyright policy in Open 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the Right retention clause is published on page 51, Programme

		<p>SUBSCRIPTION BASED JOURNAL (Elsevier, Springer Nature, Wiley...) + DEPOSIT IN AN OPEN ACCESS REPOSITORY WITH NO EMBARGO (a specific kind of Green Open Access)</p>	<p>policy finder - if an embargo period* is requested, you need to notify the publisher upon submission the Right Retention Clause to maintain the right to deposit the accepted version with no embargo - deposit the accepted version in a repository</p>	<p>Guide</p>
2) DATA	<p>- MAKE YOUR DATA FAIR [see below] - “AS OPEN AS POSSIBLE” i.e. default set to Open, keep the data closed only upon sound reasons - Data must be deposited in a “trusted repository”</p>		<p>- state that the project will responsibly manage the data according to the FAIR principles as detailed in the section FAIR Data Management [i.e. the next section in the proposal]</p>	<p>- legal basis: Open Data Directive (EU1024/2019) - definition of “trusted repository”: Annotated model Grant Agreement, p. 387</p>
3) DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)	<p>DMP IS A DELIVERABLE DUE BY MONTH 6 - DMP must be updated whenever needed</p>		<p>- state that the project will provide the DMP by month 6</p>	<p>- a DMP is a technical document to declare how you will manage your data - there are online tools to draft it - NEVER copy/paste another DMP</p>
4) MEASURES TO a) VALIDATE RESULTS b) ENSURE REPRODUCIBILITY	<p>GIVE ACCESS TO ALL THE TOOLS, SOFTWARE AND DOCUMENTATION NEEDED TO VALIDATE AND REPRODUCE - deposit in FAIR repositories all the material needed to validate and</p>		<p>- choose the right repository depending on the type of material (e.g. GitHub for software etc.) - [suggestion: create a Community in Zenodo** with the acronym of the project and deposit there</p>	<p>- it is relevant also to research integrity, to demonstrate the soundness of you research process</p>

	reproduce (you need to get a persistent identifier)		all the relevant material]	
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* embargo = months in which the paper is deposited but not visible to the public; it is requested by publishers as a form of “return on investments”

** [Zenodo](#) is an open repository powered by CERN and OpenAIRE, freely usable by anyone, accepting any type of material. Zenodo assigns a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) to any deposited item and its different versions

RECOMMENDED PRACTICES	SOME EXAMPLES/SUGGESTIONS	NOTES
The more Open science practices you adopt, the better. Your research workflow must be “as open as possible”. You can find more suggestions in the “Rainbow of Open science practices ” + Open cards and more examples in the Programme Guide pages 44-56	Pre registration of your research	Advantages: priority; no data make up; publication of negative results if the case. Tools: OSF registry or AsPredicted
	Early sharing of results as preprints	Advantages: priority, early dissemination; enabling Open peer review Tools: Pre print servers list
	Open peer review	Open peer review is often coupled with preprint servers or performed by full Open Access journals
	Publish negative results	Journal of trial and error
	E-lab open notebooks	E-lab open notebooks are digital container for texts, data, executable code (basically you have all the documentation in one place)
	Citizen Science practices	EU citizen science platform
	Co-creation, co-design	Co-creation

Beware: research assessment criteria are changing. More than 800 institutions in Europe signed [COARA](#), the reform of research assessment (including: no Impact factor, recognition of open practices and collaborative approach, recognition of all the elements of a research, not only publications).

FAIR DATA MANAGEMENT (max 1 page)

In this section you have to provide **a schema, a blueprint of the Data Management Plan** due by month 6 as a deliverable. You need to address all the sections of a DMP, but in a schematic way, e.g. by using bullet points.

The aim of this paragraph is to show the reviewer you will take care of your data responsibly (and that you are aware of the [FAIR principles](#)).

Suggestions:

- state at the beginning that the project will be conducted following the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” principle and that you will do your best effort to be “as FAIR as possible”
- if you don’t know yet what to put in one of the sections (e.g. the metadata schema you will be using) address the point anyway, with an interlocutory sentence like “a suitable metadata schema will be found either in FAIR sharing (<https://fairsharing.org/>) or in the RDA metadata standards catalogue (<https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>)”
- FAIRsharing is also the reference tool for ontologies and standards
- [Zenodo](#) is the recommended repository if in your discipline there is no repository

Sections to be covered:

TOPIC	WHAT YOU HAVE TO SPECIFY
The data the project is reusing (if so)	Which type of data + the name and URL/DOI of the database/source + the license that allows reuse
The data the project is generating and their format	Types (e.g. tabular data, images, chemical structures, surveys, geospatial data...) and format (the important issue here is if the format is a proprietary one or can be converted to an open format to ensure accessibility and interoperability)
The expected size of the data	Estimate if it's Giga, Tera... [there might be costs associated to storage and preservation, and you must budget them; so, don't be generic but try to quantify]
To be Findable	Which persistent identifier will be assigned to the dataset; which metadata schema will be used to describe the data; which versioning tool/technique
To be Accessible	Which format; which “trusted repository” are you using (=where to find the data); which access conditions: “Accessible” does not mean “Open”. Open must be the default (by law) but you might have sound reasons [to be declared here] to keep the data restricted or reserved or embargoed. Access conditions must be specified in this

	section. BEWARE: be consistent to what you state at the beginning and in the Open Science section.
To be Interoperable	Which standards are you using; which controlled vocabularies; which ontologies to unambiguously define your terms and entities
To be Reusable	Which documentation will you provide a) to ensure that your data will be correctly understood and properly reused b) to be reproducible c) to demonstrate that your research process respects research integrity rules
Ethical issues	If you need approval from an ethical committee
GDPR issues	If you are dealing with GDPR sensitive data, you need to state upon which of the 6 legal grounds you are conducting your research
Legal aspects	Any other legal aspect to be declared
Security issues	State if there is any security issue or potential dual use
Costs	Estimate the costs needed for data managing, storage and long term preservation; whether you will hire a data steward or not/who is taking care of FAIR data management
Backup and storage	Declare which backup and storage techniques and which long term preservation plan and who is responsible to do it. State which “trusted repository” are you going to use

An extended [Guide to Open Science in Horizon Europe](#) by Elena Giglia (UniTO) is available on Zenodo, with references to the official documents and links to potentially useful tools.

A [Guide to draft a DMP](#) by Gina Pavone (CNR) is available on Zenodo.